

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of some aldoses by hexacyanoferrate(III) ions in aqueous alkaline buffered medium

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Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of some aldoses like glucose, galactose, xylose and ribose by hexacyanoferrate(III) ions in aqueous alkaline buffered medium has been investigated. The kinetic results indicate the zero-order kinetics in hexacyanoferrate(III) and first-order in aldoses and OH⁻. The ionic strength of the medium has no influence on oxidation rate. Various activation parameters were also calculated at four different temperatures : 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C. The corresponding acids were identified as the main oxidation products of the reaction. A suitable mechanism consistent with experimental findings has been proposed.

Keywords : Glucose, galactose, xylose, ribose, hexacyanoferrate(III) ions, buffer.

Introduction

Oxidation of aldoses using oxidants such as *N*-bromosuccinimide, periodate, chromium(IV), vanadium(V) and chloramine-T has been carried out by several workers¹⁻⁵. The products of these oxidations were mostly aldonic acid. In the present study we now report the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of some aldoses as glucose, galactose, xylose and ribose by one electron oxidant hexacyanoferrate(III) ions (HCF(III)) in aqueous alkaline medium.

Experimental

The standard solution of glucose, galactose, xylose and ribose were always prepared a fresh in double distilled water. The other chemicals used were disodium hydrogen orthophosphate, HCF(III), sodium hydroxide, potassium chloride etc. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The reaction was carried out in thermostatic water bath at constant temperature with an accuracy of ± 0.1 °C. The reaction was started by mixing a calculated amount of aldoses in a mixture of HCF(III), sodium hydroxide, disodium hydrogen orthophosphate, KCl and water at constant pH and temperature. Disodium hydrogen orthophosphate and sodium hydroxide solutions keep the pH of the reaction mixture constant. In separate experiment it has been found that disodium hydrogen orthophosphate does not react with any of the reactant. The progress of the reaction was measured iodometrically⁶. The initial rate values in terms of $(-dc/dt)$ were evaluated by plane mirror method from the plot of remaining concentration of

HCF(III) vs time (*t*). For first-order reaction linear plot was plotted between rates and concentration. Least square method was used for best fit line in the graphical plots^{7,8}. First-order rate constant were calculated from the slope of $\log(a-x)$ vs time plots. The products were identified by paper chromatography in comparison with the oxidation product of glucose, galactose, xylose and ribose by bromine water separately. A solvent system of *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 5) was used and detection was carried out with alkaline silver nitrate⁹. Evidence for the formation of an enediol is furnished by observed ability to alkaline solution of carbohydrates to decolorize solution of 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenol¹⁰. Gluconic acid, galactonic acid, xylonic acid and ribonic acid were identified as the main oxidation products of reaction.

Results and discussion

In the present work, the kinetics of oxidation of glucose, galactose, xylose and ribose by HCF(III) in aqueous alkaline buffered medium obtained by disodium hydrogen orthophosphate and sodium hydroxide has been studied.

Effect of pH : Table 1 presents the data of reaction rate at different pH, for the oxidation of glucose, galactose, xylose and ribose. From the data it is revealed that initially reaction rate increase with the increase of pH but it suddenly rises after pH 11.8 in the oxidation of glucose and xylose. In case of galactose and ribose such high rate is observed after pH 11.4 and 11.35 respectively. It may occur due to the fast transformation of α to β form or vice

versa resulting into the high reaction rates. It has also been reported that at about pH 9.2, β form oxidizes about 28 times faster than α form^{11,12}. In the present study the rate of oxidation has been studied at pH 11.45 and 11.35 at which the reaction occurs with measurable rate.

Table 1. Effect of pH on reaction rate

Overall concentration of HCF(III) and sugar	pH	$[-dc/dt] \times 10^5$ (M min ⁻¹)
Glucose : $1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ HCF(III) : $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	10.80	0.50
	11.20	1.50
	11.45	3.00
	11.60	3.50
	11.80	6.70
Galactose : $1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ HCF(III) : $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	12.20	13.33
	10.40	0.40
	10.55	0.50
	10.80	0.80
	11.35	1.60
Xylose : $1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ HCF(III) : $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	11.40	1.80
	12.20	4.00
	10.55	0.60
	10.80	0.80
	11.35	1.60
Ribose : $1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ HCF(III) : $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	11.50	2.00
	11.80	2.80
	12.20	5.00
	10.55	0.60
	10.85	1.00
	11.20	1.80
	11.35	2.50
	11.70	5.00
	12.00	5.50

Effect of HCF(III) : The order of the reaction with respect to HCF(III) ion concentration was determined at fixed concentrations of other reactants and at constant temperature and pH. The concentration of HCF(III) has been varied from 1.00×10^{-3} to $6.00 \times 10^{-3} M$. The data show zero-order kinetics with respect to HCF(III) ion. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Effect of substrate : From Table 2, it is observed that the reaction follows first-order kinetics with respect to glucose, galactose, xylose and ribose concentration. In all cases substrate concentration was varied from 0.50×10^{-2}

to $6.00 \times 10^{-2} M$. The linear plot of $\log [\text{rate}]$ vs $\log [S]$ with unit slope also indicates first-order dependence on $[S]$.

Effect of hydroxyl ions : The data presented in Table 2 clearly reveals that reaction rate increases directly with the increase of hydroxide ion concentration. Pseudo-first-order rate constant does not change with the increase of hydroxide ion concentration. Thus the reaction follows first-order kinetics with respect to hydroxide ion concentration.

Table 2. Effect of [reactant] on the reaction rate at 35 °C

[HCF(III)] $\times 10^{-3} M$	[S] $\times 10^{-2} M$	[OH] $\times 10^{-3} M$	$[-dc/dt] \times 10^5$ (M min ⁻¹)			
			Glucose	Galac- tose	Xylose	Ribose
1.00	3.00	–	6.30	2.92	5.03	4.53
2.00	3.00	–	7.04	2.95	5.13	4.64
3.00	3.00	–	7.12	2.73	4.85	4.82
4.00	3.00	–	7.23	2.91	4.98	4.92
5.00	3.00	–	7.18	2.88	4.85	5.09
6.00	3.00	–	–	2.92	5.18	5.00
3.00	0.50	–	1.00	0.40	0.42	1.50
3.00	1.00	–	2.50	0.83	1.33	3.00
3.00	2.00	–	4.28	1.67	2.00	5.83
3.00	3.00	–	6.00	2.50	3.00	8.00
3.00	4.00	–	8.00	3.50	3.33	11.00
3.00	5.00	–	10.00	4.30	4.00	14.00
3.00	6.00	–	–	5.00	5.00	16.67
1.00	1.00	1.00	–	0.20	–	0.20
1.00	1.00	2.00	–	0.40	0.60	0.50
1.00	1.00	3.00	0.40	0.62	0.89	0.70
1.00	1.00	4.00	0.50	0.77	1.20	0.90
1.00	1.00	5.00	0.67	0.93	1.45	1.10
1.00	1.00	6.00	0.80	1.10	1.73	1.30
1.00	1.00	7.00	0.90	–	2.00	–
1.00	1.00	8.00	1.00	–	2.36	–

Effect of the previous treatment of aldoses with sodium hydroxide on the reaction rate : The effect of previous treatment of above said aldoses and keto sugar fructose with hydroxide ions on reaction rate has been studied. The data are presented in Table 3. A perusal of the results presented in Table 3 clearly reveals that as the time of treatment of glucose, galactose, xylose and ribose with sodium hydroxide increases, the rate of reaction also

increases. But in case of fructose the rate of reaction decreases with the increase of time of alkali treatment. It is well known that when the reducing sugars are treated with the alkali, the base catalysed Lobry de-Bruyn transformation takes place. When an aldehyde sugar is treated with alkali equilibrium between keto sugar produced and aldehyde one is established. On other hand in case of keto sugar after treatment with alkali equilibrium is established between the aldehyde sugar produced and keto one taken¹³

Table 3. Effect of previous treatment of aldoses with NaOH
[HCF(III)] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ M, Temp. = 35 °C

	Overall concn. of aldoses and alkali	Time of treatment (h)	[-dC/dt] × 10 ⁵ (M min ⁻¹)
Glucose	1.00 × 10 ⁻² M	0	2.60
		2	3.20
NaOH	1.00 × 10 ⁻² M	4	3.60
Galactose	1.00 × 10 ⁻² M	0	1.50
		2	5.20
NaOH	1.00 × 10 ⁻² M	4	8.60
Xylose	1.00 × 10 ⁻² M	0	2.80
		2	3.40
NaOH	1.00 × 10 ⁻² M	4	3.80
Ribose	1.00 × 10 ⁻² M	0	2.50
		2	3.20
NaOH	1.00 × 10 ⁻² M	4	3.50
Fructose	0.50 × 10 ⁻² M	0	4.50
		3	4.20
NaOH	1.60 × 10 ⁻² M	5	0.67

Effect of ionic strength : The effect of ionic strength on the rate of oxidation was studied by using solution of KCl. No appreciable salt effect was detected.

Table 4. Effect of ionic strength on the reaction rate
[HCF(III)] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M, [S] = 1.00 × 10⁻², Temp. = 35 °C

μ (M)	[-dC/dt] × 10 ⁵ (M min ⁻¹)			
	Glucose	Galactose	Xylose	Ribose
0.20	4.00	0.80	1.70	1.70
0.50	4.00	0.80	1.60	1.70
0.75	4.00	0.77	1.60	1.60
1.00	4.00	0.80	1.60	1.60

Effect of temperature : The activation parameters like energy of activation (ΔE_a), entropy of activation (ΔS*), enthalpy (ΔH*) were calculated from the measurement of the rate at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K. The activation

parameters were evaluated from log k versus 1/T plots. The values are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Activation parameters

Sugar	E _a (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Frequency factor A × 10 ¹⁰ (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	-ΔS* (EU)	ΔH* (kcal mol ⁻¹)	ΔF* (kcal mol ⁻¹)
Glucose	15.92	1.52	14.03	15.30	19.65
Galactose	16.88	3.14	12.52	16.26	20.15
Xylose	16.10	1.33	14.22	15.48	19.90
Ribose	16.10	1.04	15.42	15.49	20.27

Stoichiometry : The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied in excess of oxidant concentration. The stoichiometry was found to involve 2 moles of HCF(III) for each mole of aldoses. The stoichiometry can be shown by the following equation.

N = 6 for glucose and galactose, n = 5 for xylose and ribose.

Mechanism : From the study of the experimental results it seems possible that the rate determining step in oxidation of the above said aldoses with HCF(III) is the action of hydroxyl ion on aldoses leading to the formation of an enediol ion intermediate (step I). This intermediate subsequently gets oxidized by HCF(III), which is a faster step (step II). The second step explains the independency of the reaction rate with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) ions. The following mechanism is proposed.

where S and en⁻ represent the aldoses and intermediate enediol ion. Based upon the above proposed mechanism the following rate law has been derived,

$$-\frac{d[HCF(III)]}{dt} = k_1[S][OH^-] \quad (1)$$

The derived rate law (1) clearly accounts for the first-order kinetics both with respect to aldoses and hydroxyl ion,

and zero-order kinetics with respect to [HCF(III)] which are in good agreement with experimental results.

The straight line plots between rate^{-1} vs $[\text{S}]^{-1}$ and rate^{-1} vs $[\text{OH}^{-}]^{-1}$ confirm the proposed rate law. The values of k_1 are calculated from the slopes of these curves. Degree of agreement in these values of k_1 and calculated from $\log(a-x)$ vs time plots again confirm the proposed rate law.

Name of substrate	Value of k_1 (min^{-1})		
	Rate ⁻¹ vs [S] ⁻¹	Rate ⁻¹ vs [OH] ⁻¹	$\log(a-x)$ vs t
Glucose	0.040	0.044	0.04602
Galactose	0.075	0.044	0.01958
Xylose	0.045	0.030	0.0300
Ribose	0.029	0.029	0.02994

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